

Techno-economic assessment of the multi-absorber approach at an industrial site with multiple CO₂ sources

Andressa Nakao

Department of Chemical Engineering, NTNU, NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway

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ABSTRACT

To meet the goals of the Paris Agreement, decarbonization across all sectors, including industrial facilities with multiple CO₂ emission sources, is essential. Post-combustion capture, despite its high energy demands, is a promising technology for reducing carbon emissions. This study explores the feasibility of CO₂ capture using a multi-absorber/combined-stripper system at an industrial refinery. CO₂ capture was modeled using 30 wt.% MEA for four stacks, optimizing each to minimize energy use while achieving 95 % capture. The study also examines CO₂ capture costs, operational expenses, and unit size requirements.

Results indicate that the multi-absorber/combined-stripper configuration required less solvent and had lower reboiler duties compared to individual absorber setups, though it required higher initial investment for larger equipment. Compared to flue gas mixing, the multi-absorber/combined-stripper system had higher equipment costs but lower operating expenses. While flue gas mixing had lower equipment costs, it incurred significantly higher transportation costs depending on the distance between sources and the capture site.

A sensitivity analysis on packing and steam costs showed that a 50 % reduction in packing costs could lower capital expenses by 10–30 %, while reduced steam costs could cut operating expenses by 25 %. This analysis highlights areas where cost reductions could make CO₂ capture more economically viable.

Abbreviations

A	surface area in m ²
AAD	absolute average deviation
AARD	absolute average relative deviation
B ₂	parameter specified for each equipment (Eq. (9))
CAPEX	capital expenditure
C _{base year}	purchased equipment cost
C _{BM}	bare module cost
C _{cont}	expenses related to contingencies
C _{fee}	expenses related to other charges
C _{GR}	grassroot cost
C _{OL}	labor costs
C _p ⁰	purchased cost for base conditions
C _{RM}	raw materials cost
C _{TM}	total equipment cost
C _{UT}	costs of utilities
C _{WT}	waste treatment cost
CCS	carbon capture and storage

CEPCI	chemical engineering plant cost index
COM	total manufacturing cost
CS	carbon steel
D	column diameter in m
DCC	direct contact cooler
F _p	parameter that incorporate different operating pressure (Eq. (9))
GDP	gross domestic product
GHG	greenhouse gas
IPCC	intergovernmental panel on climate change
K ₂	parameters characteristic for each unit (Eq. (10))
K ₃	parameters characteristic for each unit (Eq. (10))
L/G	liquid and gas ratio in kg/kg
MEA	monoethanolamine
n	number of experimental data
NGCC	natural gas combined cycle
SRD	specific reboiler duty in [GJ / tonCO ₂]
TPC	total plant cost
ΔT _{lm}	log mean temperature difference in °C

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: hanna.knuutila@ntnu.no (H.K. Knuutila).

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ΔT_i	fluid i temperature difference in °C
U_i	overall heat transfer coefficient
v	gas superficial velocity in m/s
\dot{V}	gas volumetric flow rate in m ³ /s
VLE	vapor liquid equilibrium
x_i	relative error
\bar{x}	mean

1. Introduction

In 2023, total energy-related CO₂ emissions increased by 1.1 %, underscoring the challenge of achieving the global climate goals outlined in the Paris Agreement (IEA, 2024). The industrial sector is the second-largest emitter of CO₂, following the power sector, and accounts for approximately one-quarter of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (IEA, 2019; de Pee et al., 2018). Decarbonizing this sector is critical yet challenging due to technical and economic constraints (IEA, 2019; Rissman et al., 2020).

Carbon capture and storage (CCS) is recognized as a key strategy for achieving emissions reductions in the industrial sector. Among various capture technologies, post-combustion capture using aqueous amines is particularly promising for retrofitting existing industrial facilities. Extensive studies have demonstrated its effectiveness, with a 90 % CO₂ capture rate widely accepted as a benchmark for economic and environmental performance (Roussanaly et al., 2021a; Griffiths, 2022; Du, 2021). As emphasized in recent literature (Sunny et al., 2022; Feron et al., 2019), attaining carbon capture rates surpassing 90 % is crucial in the pursuit of achieving net-zero emissions. Amines are well-suited for capturing CO₂ from flue gas streams due to their high reactivity and easy scalability, making them the leading candidate for industrial applications (Sunny et al., 2022; Feron et al., 2019). However, the deployment of CO₂ capture systems in industrial settings faces practical challenges, including spatial constraints, safety regulations, and the need for substantial capital investment (Roussanaly et al., 2021a).

Previous work in this area has explored various configurations to optimize the performance and cost-effectiveness of amine-based absorption systems in industrial settings. For example, van Straelen et al. (2010) examined strategies for combining emissions from multiple sources into a single point-source capture system, simplifying operations but increasing infrastructure complexity. Decentralized setups, where individual CO₂ capture plants are installed at each emission point, offer flexibility but require higher investment and coordination. Recent

studies have also investigated the potential of multi-absorber/combined-stripper configurations, which streamline operations and reduce capital expenditure compared to single large-scale absorber/stripper systems (van Straelen et al., 2010; Tobiesen and Schumann-Olsen, 2011).

This work focuses on the implementation of CO₂ capture in a refinery, an industrial cluster with multiple CO₂ emission sources. Using process simulations, three strategies for absorption-based CO₂ capture with aqueous amines were evaluated: (1) combining multiple CO₂ sources into a single capture plant, (2) deploying multiple capture plants at individual sources, and (3) employing a multi-absorber/combined-stripper concept. Each approach was assessed for its energy and cost implications, providing insights into carbon capture solutions in industrial environments.

1.1. CO₂ capture plant based on aqueous amine

As mentioned before, the global commitment to mitigating climate change has led to a surge in research and development efforts aimed at improving the efficiency of CO₂ capture technologies. Among various approaches, processes based on aqueous amines have shown promise in capturing CO₂ from industrial flue gases. Fig. 1 shows a conventional CO₂ capture plant based on aqueous amine.

In the absorber column, the CO₂-containing flue gas ascends from the bottom, while the solvent descends from the top, creating a counter-current contact between the gas and the liquid, allowing the amine solvent to chemically bind with the CO₂.

The treated flue gas, now containing only a fraction of the CO₂, undergoes a water wash on the top of the absorber column to minimize solvent emissions into the atmosphere and maintain the water balance. Additional countermeasures may be necessary in real plants to ensure that the solvent emissions remain within regulatory limits (Buvik, 2021).

The bottom outlet liquid stream, known as rich amine, is pumped to the top of the stripper via a heat exchanger. The rich amine is regenerated within the stripper, typically at around 2 bar pressure and temperatures up to around 120 °C, to reverse the CO₂ absorption reactions. To sustain the required regeneration conditions in the stripper, a steam reboiler is employed at the bottom, providing the required heat and stripping steam. The energy consumed by the reboiler constitutes the most significant component of the energy input in the CO₂ absorption-based capture plant.

Fig. 1. A conventional CO₂ amine-based capture plant.

At the top of the stripper, the outlet vapor stream, rich in CO₂, passes through water recovery within a condenser and a drum. The water is reintroduced to the stripper while the gaseous CO₂ product is sent for further processing.

The solvent with residual CO₂ content, known as the lean solvent, is pumped back to the absorber via the same heat exchanger mentioned above and a cooler, reducing its temperature before re-entering the absorber.

This study centers on the CO₂ removal process from the main stacks of a conventional refinery, establishing various case studies employing the multi-absorber/one-stripper concept for assessment and comparison. Furthermore, the primary equipment will be appropriately sized and subjected to economic evaluation. The investigation aims to connect a single absorber/combined-stripper concept with a multi-absorber/combined-stripper concept, critically analyzing the merits and drawbacks of each scenario. Key parameters, including absorber size, energy consumption, and equipment cost, will be thoroughly examined. In actual refinery operations, multi-source CO₂ capture presents an intricate optimization challenge. The feasibility analysis of such a system should also encompass considerations such as (i) operational simplicity, (ii) the distance between stacks to be treated, and (iii) available area. This work will include a qualitative discussion of these factors, elucidating their real-world implications and limitations.

2. Case study: a large conversion refinery

Refineries host a variety of CO₂ emission sources, each with distinct characteristics and functions. In the refinery scenario, the primary contributors are the power stations, the fluid catalytic unit, the distillation units, and the steam methane reformer (Sunny et al., 2022). Power stations often integrate a natural gas combined cycle (NGCC) plant, with additional gas-fired boilers to cover the refinery's power needs (Du, 2021). Further, the heat demands of the atmospheric and vacuum distillation units are satisfied through the combustion of fuel oil and gases. The steam methane reformer relies on natural gas both as a feedstock and a fuel, resulting in two distinct CO₂ emission points (Du, 2021). Furthermore, smaller units such as heaters, boilers, and gas turbines commonly operate using fuel gases, fuel oil, or natural gas. These diverse emission points exhibit a relatively low CO₂ concentration, typically around 8 % volume, but have the potential to collectively release substantial volumes of CO₂ (van Straelen et al., 2010). Further, the CO₂ sources in a large refinery can be divided into three categories based on their costs (van Straelen et al., 2010):

- (i) smaller costs, such as high pressure and high concentration sources, e.g., hydrogen production.
- (ii) reasonable costs, such as large flue gas sources as emissions from furnaces and gas turbines.
- (iii) higher costs, as, for example, small emissions sources with a low concentration of CO₂ spread throughout the refinery. These would be the most expensive to mitigate, and the geographic location of each source could impact the cost due to, for example, the need of additional ducting and piping.

The current research chose flue gases with diverse characteristics, representing various CO₂ sources, aiming to assess their impact on the viability of the plant implementation.

2.1. Case description

Four distinct sources of CO₂, denoted as A, B, C, and D, were investigated. These sources were based on the CO₂ content range of typical units from a large refinery (van Straelen et al., 2010; IEAGHG, 2017a) and are presented in Table 1. Two assumptions were made: (i) all the flue gas streams were pre-treated (no NO_x or SO_x present) and (ii) the flue gas streams were saturated with water.

Table 1
Characterization of the studied CO₂ sources.

ID	Molar fraction (%)			Flue Gas [Nm ³ /s]
	CO ₂	H ₂ O	inert	
A	4.0	7.3	remaining	327.78
B	8.5	7.3	remaining	103.08
C	11.0	7.3	remaining	51.32
D	20.0	7.3	remaining	25.81

The current study involved conducting three sets of simulations of CO₂ amine-based capture plants using 30 wt.% monoethanolamine as solvent. In Set I, individual CO₂ capture plants were deployed for each emission source, and their respective performances were evaluated. Set II focused on exploring permutations related to the combination of various CO₂ sources, incorporating multiple absorbers, and adopting a combined-stripper approach for each possible permutation. Set III incorporated the permutations explored in Set II. However, in this instance, the flue gas streams were mixed for each permutation, and a CO₂ capture plant was implemented for each mixture. Fig. 2 provides a simplified diagram illustrating the studied cases.

As depicted in Fig. 2, each individual source in this study has been labelled with an ID letter as shown in Table 1: A, B, C, D. The simulations of each individual CO₂ capture plant corresponding to these sources will bear the respective letter ID in their tags. For cases explored in Set II, where a multiple-absorber/ combined-stripper approach was applied, the tag will include the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B refers to the implementation of an individual absorber for each source, A and B, and only one stripper). In Set III, simulations characterized by the mixing of different flue gas streams will have the letters of the sources in their tags continuously without spaces between them (e.g., AB means that the flue gas from sources A and B were mixed, with this case having only one absorber and one stripper). In all cases, we sought the optimal condition, which corresponds to the minimum energy requirement for the regeneration unit. Finally, the different cases simulated (sets I, II, and III) were combined to compare the alternatives for capturing 95 % of CO₂ from the four CO₂ emission sources (sources A, B, C, and D).

2.2. Models and tools

The simulation work employed CO2SIM software version 7.1. The SINTEF CO2SIM process simulator is an internally developed flow sheet simulator framework created collaboratively by SINTEF and NTNU (Tobiesen et al., 2007). CO2SIM offers a versatile and comprehensive simulation platform designed to simulate carbon dioxide (CO₂) capture processes.

This rate-based simulator has been extensively utilized for several purposes, including the development of solvents, configuration studies, and performance assessments of various solvent systems intended for post-combustion CO₂ capture absorption processes. CO2SIM's numerical solvers allow to simulate and optimize different intricate process configurations. Several published works give a more in-depth description of the specific models employed within CO2SIM (Tobiesen and Schumann-Olsen, 2011; Tobiesen et al., 2007; Tobiesen et al., 2008; Tobiesen et al., 2018).

2.3. Model validation

Model validation is a fundamental step in model development. It is essential to demonstrate the agreement between the simulations' results and the experimental data of the modelled system. To provide an accurate model, it is important to perform validation against data from different plants, preferably under a different range of operating conditions. For this analysis, the relative error (x_r), the Absolute Average Deviation (AAD), and the Absolute Average Relative Deviation (AARD)

Fig. 2. Simplified diagram of the studied cases.

(Tobiesen et al., 2007) were calculated, as shown below.

$$x_i = \frac{v_{sim} - v_{exp}}{v_{exp}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

In the Eq. (1) v_{sim} and v_{exp} are the studied variables found from the simulations and experimental data, respectively.

The percentage deviation was further used to find the Absolute Average Deviation (AAD) and Absolute Average Relative Deviation (AARD), which were calculated using the following formulas:

$$AARD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| \quad (2)$$

$$AAD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - \bar{x}| \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n} \quad (4)$$

From Eqs. (2) to (4), n is the number of experimental data.

Equilibrium curves for CO₂ in a solution of 30 wt.% MEA solution were simulated using CO2SIM through flash simulations to assess the model's capability in predicting vapor-liquid equilibrium (VLE) and compared with literature data from Aronu et al. (2011). The comparison between simulation results and experimental data can be seen in Fig. 3.

The CO2SIM VLE model has demonstrated considerable accuracy across all the temperature range investigated. The VLE model has shown a minor overestimation of the CO₂ partial pressure for 40 and 60 °C for CO₂ loadings ranging between 0.3 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{MEA} and 0.5 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{MEA}. A minor overestimation of the CO₂ partial pressure in this range

would result in a slightly reduced absorption rate, which would, in turn, lead to a slightly higher solvent demand to achieve the required capture.

The operating temperature of the stripper in this work is approximately 120 °C. The model shows a slight underprediction for loadings below 0.3 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{MEA} and a slight overestimation for loadings above 0.3 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{MEA}. An underprediction of the lean loading would suggest that more CO₂ is being stripped, which would, in turn, indicate a slight overprediction of the reboiler duty required to reach the lean loading value.

The AAD and AARD values can be found in Table S1 in Supporting information. Overall, the AARD for the CO₂ partial pressure was 17.57 %, which is deemed acceptable and in line with other models available in the literature (Aronu et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2011).

For the process model validation, process simulations were conducted. Experimental data from pilot campaigns has been used. The absorber and stripper columns were initially simulated independently. In this part, data from Tobiesen et al. (2007) and Tobiesen et al. (2008) was used. In the pilot, the absorber has a diameter of 0.15 m and a packing height of 4.36 m, while the desorber has a diameter of 0.1 m and a packing height is 3.89 m. Both columns use Mellapak 250Y as packing material. Input parameters for the model included flow rates, composition, temperatures, and pressures of the inlet streams, along with the reboiler duty in the stripper simulations. In the absorber segment (Aronu et al., 2011), a total of 20 experimental runs were simulated (Tobiesen et al., 2007), while the stripper segment involved 19 simulated experimental runs (Tobiesen et al., 2008). The entire plant simulation was performed and compared with in-house data. from a pilot at SINTEF's Tiller CO₂ lab.

In the absorber simulations, the comparison between simulated and experimental data involved assessing the CO₂ captured, rich loading, and outlet stream temperatures. The absorber results indicate a very

Fig. 3. Semi-Log Plot of CO₂ partial pressure versus CO₂ loading for temperatures from 40 °C to 120 °C, comparing simulation and experimental data.

good prediction on temperature profiles, with an Average Absolute Deviation (AAD) below 2 %. However, there is an underprediction in the amount of CO₂ absorbed, with an AAD of 11.0 %. The rich loading also showed a slight underprediction with an AAD of 1.7 %. The stripper model represents the temperature profiles very well, also with an AAD below 1 %- the CO₂ desorbed is slightly overpredicted with an AAD of 12 %. There is an underprediction on the lean loading, resulting in an AAD of 4.9 %. The in-house full pilot plant data has shown an AAD of 4.4 % of the CO₂ desorbed, an underprediction of the loading, resulting in an AAD of 11.3 % for the lean loading and 1.6 % for the rich loading.

Overall, the validation showed that the simulation tool provided trustworthy results. The absorber and stripper validation results can be found in Tables S2 to S5 as part of the supplementary information.

2.4. CO₂SIM capture model

For this study, a simulation model was developed based on Fig. 1. It was assumed that the flue gas was already saturated and at the appropriate operating conditions—at a temperature of 40 °C and pressure of 101.325 kPa. Furthermore, the water wash section was replaced with a condenser to maintain the water balance in the simulations. These assumptions were made to reduce the computational workload and minimize the number of loops, ensuring optimal numerical performance. For clarity, the flowsheet of the simulation model can be found in the Supplementary information, section S8. The assumptions and specifications used in the simulations are described in the following subsection. The list of unit operations included in the model is presented in Table 2.

The practical implementation of multi-source CO₂ capture within industrial clusters presents a complex optimization challenge. Thus, the simulations were divided into three sets, as discussed below.

Table 2

List of unit operations included on the CO₂SIM model.

On CO ₂ SIM flowsheet		
Type	ID	Description
Columns	Absorber	Absorption column
	Stripper	Regeneration column
Heat Exchangers	Hex01	Lean/Rich heat exchanger
	Condenser01	Responsible for keeping the water balance of the simulation
	Condenser02	Water recovery from the regeneration
	Cooler01	Lean amine cooler
Pump	Reboiler	Providing stripping steam and heat
	Rich Pump	To ensure that there is no solvent flashing in the heat exchanger
Controller	Con01	Responsible for the solvent makeup stream

2.4.1. Set I—individual CO₂ capture plant

Set I follow the conventional CO₂ capture approach, an individual plant for an individual source, with the study aiming to identify the optimal operating conditions for each individual source.

In this scenario, retrofitting a CO₂ capture plant close to each source at the industrial site would be a straightforward option. This would indicate the absence of spatial constraints and an existing infrastructure providing the necessary support for optimal performance.

This set will thoroughly examine key factors such as the absorber packing height, solvent loadings, solvent amount, and energy requirements. The results obtained will be explored and utilized in the subsequent sets of this study.

2.4.2. Set II—multi-absorber combined-stripper approach

The focus of Set II centres around the multi-absorber/combined-

stripper approach. In this approach, there is an absorption column exclusive for each source of CO₂ and a centralized area for the stripper column. This setup would be suitable for industrial sites facing constraints that make it challenging to hold an entire CO₂ capture plant. However, it would allow the installation of an absorption column close to the source. Due to only having one stripper, this configuration requires the implementation of pipes to transport the solvent to and from the regeneration site. Additionally, in Set II, the lean/rich heat exchanger is located on the regeneration side, designed to handle all the outlet liquid streams from each absorber. Heat losses due to long transport distances were not considered in the simulations.

A distinct aspect of this approach is that, when utilizing a combined-stripper, the lean loading remains constant for the absorbers. This factor can significantly impact the solvent amount required to achieve a given capture rate, influencing the required reboiler duty for the same purpose.

In this case study, four procedures were used:

- 1) The optimal liquid-to-gas ratios, L/G, found for individual absorbers were kept as found in Set I
- 2) The lean loading of the absorber from Set I, with the highest lean loading, was used as lean loading from the combined stripper. The L/G of the second absorber was then simulated using this lean loading.
- 3) The lean loading of the absorber from Set I with the lowest lean loading was used as lean loading from the combined stripper. The L/G of the second absorber was then simulated using this lean loading.
- 4) In this case, the overall L/G was calculated based on the weighted average between the L/G of the optimal absorbers. The insights gained from this brief investigation have been applied to the other permutations on Set II, which involve more than two sources.

From these, the case showing minimum reboiler duty was selected as optimum. The difference between the optimums of different approaches was small due to the characteristics of the solvent. In all cases, rich loadings close to maximum (0.5 mol_{CO2}/mol_{MEA}) were reached. More details about these procedures can be found in Section S5 in the Supplementary information.

2.4.3. Set III—mixing flue gas approach

Set III closely resembles Set I in terms of implementing one absorber and one stripper configuration. However, in Set III, the flue gas is transported to a central area where the CO₂ capture plant is situated. In these instances, both columns will be larger to accommodate the necessary volume of flue gas that needs treatment.

This strategy presents a potential option for existing industrial facilities constrained by space or those not originally designed to allocate larger capture equipment close to a source. In real life, it is important to take into account considerations related to the safety regulations governing the redirection of flue gas and the logistical requirements and costs associated.

2.5. Specifications of the unit operations

2.5.1. Columns

The specifications of the absorber and stripper columns can be found in Table 3. The absorber packing height for each case study is part of the simulation work and was determined based on a sensitivity analysis conducted in a previous study (Nakao et al., 2022). It will vary based on the flue gas CO₂ content and the designated CO₂ capture rate (Nakao et al., 2022). A more detailed discussion of the packing height selection process can be found in the supplementary file, Section S2. Mellapak 250Y (Sulzer) was used as packing material (Tobiesen et al., 2007; Tobiesen et al., 2008). The diameter was calculated based on the gas velocity, as shown in Eq. (5). In this scenario, the gas superficial velocity (*v*) was set as 2 m/s, suitable for Mellapak 250Y packing (Park and Øi, 2017).

Table 3
Specifications for the unit operations.

Parameter	Value/specification	Comments/reference(s)
Absorber Packing	Mellapak 250Y	(Tobiesen et al., 2007)
Diameter [m]	Calculated based on the flue gas volumetric flow rate and the gas superficial velocity	Eq. (5)
Gas superficial velocity [m/s]	2	(Park and Øi, 2017)
Packing Height [m]	Calculated based on the capture rate for each study case	–
Capture rate (% of incoming CO ₂ content)	95	–
Stripper Packing	Mellapak 250Y	(Tobiesen et al., 2008)
Diameter[m]	60% of the Absorber Diameter	–
Packing Height [m]	Fixed for each case study	–
Lean/Rich Heat Exchanger Temperature of approach [K]	10 K between the lean amine outlet and the rich amine inlet streams	(Aromada, 2020, van der Spek et al., 2019)
Lean Cooler		
Lean Amine outlet stream temperature [K]	313.15	–
Lean Amine outlet stream pressure [kPa]	101.325	–
Condensers		
Process outlet stream temperature [K]	313.15	–
Process outlet stream pressure [kPa]	Top of absorber - 101.325 Top of the stripper - 190	–
Reboiler		
Operating pressure [kPa]	190	–
Reboiler Duty [kJ/h]	Calculated for each study case	–
Rich Pump		
Pressure [kPa]	1000	–
Isentropic efficiency (%)	75	(Turton; and Whiting, 2018)

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4\dot{V}}{\pi v}} \quad (5)$$

In the equation *D* is the column diameter in *m*, \dot{V} the gas volumetric flow rate in m³/s and *v* is the gas superficial velocity in m/s.

The stripper column also requires the specification of the geometric parameters. The diameter was fixed to 60 % of the absorber diameter calculated with the total volumetric gas flow rate to be treated for each case, and the height was fixed to 12 m.

2.5.2. Heat exchangers

The model has five heat exchangers. Their specifications can be found on Table 3.

The lean/rich heat exchanger, Hex01, facilitates the exchange between the incoming rich amine flow from the absorber and the outgoing lean amine stream from the reboiler. A temperature approach of 10 °C between the inlet of the rich amine and the outlet of the lean amine was used as input specification.

The lean amine cooler, Cooler01, cools the lean solvent down to 40 °C before it enters the absorber column.

On the top of the stripper, a condenser recovers the water from the stripper outlet. This condenser, condenser02, was set as a flash, the pressure value was set as 190 kPa and the temperature was 40 °C. In the reboiler, the pressure was set to 190 kPa and the reboiler duty value was

changed until the desired capture rate was achieved.

Finally, as mentioned before, the water wash system was replaced by a condenser, condenser01, to reduce the computational time and help keep the water balance in the simulations. The condenser01 was simulated with a flash unit, in which the pressure was set to 101.325 kPa and the temperature 40 °C.

2.5.3. Pumps

Pumps will be required in different places in the capture plant. The impact of the pumps on the simulation results is small. Thus, only the rich pump, Pump01, was included. This pump is used to avoid multiphase flow in the rich/lean heat exchanger. The pressure was set to 1000 kPa. The data used for the rich amine pump is shown in Table 3.

3. Sizing and cost estimation

This section will present the assumptions made for the sizing step and cost estimation.

As previously stated, not all components of an amine-based CO₂ capture system were simulated. However, there are several units that can have a significant impact on the cost, even though their impact on the simulations is insignificant. Thus, five additional pumps, the blower prior to the absorber, two storage tanks, and water wash columns were sized, even though they were not added in the simulation flowsheet. An overview of the units that are added to the sizing and cost estimation is provided in Table 4. All heat exchangers and pumps were assumed to be installed at ground level.

3.1. Sizing

3.1.1. Columns

In absorption-based CO₂ capture, the absorber is one of the most expensive equipment (Aromada, 2020; Karimi et al., 2011; Singh et al., 2003; Tuinier et al., 2011; Ali et al., 2019; Mores et al., 2012; Berghout et al., 2013; Aromada et al., 2021; Aromada et al., 2022). Generally, for many amines, this means that to attain higher levels of CO₂ capture, one can either increase the height of the absorber packing or pay more for solvent regeneration through increased specific reboiler duty (SRD) (Su, 2023). On the other hand, increasing the packing height leads to a greater residence time and promotes a larger contact surface area between the solvent and the flue gas in the absorber. Therefore, as the residence time increases, the rich loading increases, which results in a decrease in the amount of solvent required. A smaller amount of solvent and higher rich loading result in a lower heat requirement in the reboiler, reducing the SRD (Su, 2023).

Table 4
Additional units included on the cost assessment.

Additional units		
Type	ID	Description
Pumps	Lean Pump	Responsible for the lean amine flow between the stripper and the absorber
	Stripper condenser pump	Responsible for the liquid flow on the top of the stripper
	Cooling water pump	Responsible for the flow rates for the cooling water required on the plant
	Water Wash pump	Responsible for the liquid flow on the water wash section
	Make Up pump	Responsible for the makeup flow on the top of the system
Compressor	Blower	Responsible for the inlet Gas flow of the absorber
Tank	Amine storage tank	Storage of the solvent for make-up
	Process water tank	Storage for the process water
Column	Water Wash	Responsible for the water balance and to reduce solvent loss

The present study uses specifications based on a published study, (Nakao et al., 2022).

According to Duss and Menon (2010), the absorber units are recommended to have a diameter of 16 m or less. Beyond these thresholds, the uniform distribution of both phases, particularly vapor distribution, becomes challenging (van der Spek et al., 2019; Duss and Menon, 2010). Thus, in some cases involving the combination of different CO₂ stacks, two absorbers in parallel were deemed necessary. In these cases, the flue gas was evenly divided into two streams, and the absorber diameter was recalculated based on the updated volumetric gas flow rate. These cases are identified with a * on their labels. This decision did not impact the packing height. For the overall column height, the design recommendations by van der Spek et al. (2019) and Kvamsdal et al. (2010) were used, Table 5.

To prevent CO₂ evaporation in both the heat exchanger and the feed line leading to the stripper, a pressure of 1000 kPa was used, as stated earlier. A throttle valve was placed prior to the stripper inlet to reduce the pressure to that of the stripper. After the throttle valve, the solvent is directed into a flash vessel positioned directly above the stripper packing within the column (Notz et al., 2012). This configuration ensures the safeguarding of the packing from the potential impact of the incoming two-phase stream.

Although the simulation model has a condenser instead of a water wash column on the top of the absorber, the cost assessment step includes a water wash column. Its design involves matching the same diameter of the absorber column, as an extra section above, with a fixed packing height of 4 m (Dinh, 2023), as it is shown in Table 6.

3.1.2. Heat exchangers

Designing a heat exchanger involves determining the required surface area (A), which is calculated from the necessary heat duty (Q_i), overall heat transfer coefficient (U_i) and the inlet and outlet streams' temperatures. In this work, the log mean temperature difference, LMTD, method was used (Incropera et al., 2011), according to Eq. (6):

$$Q_i = U_i A \Delta T_{lm} \quad (6)$$

where ΔT_{lm} is the log mean temperature difference and can be calculated as:

$$\Delta T_{lm} = \frac{\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2}{\ln(\Delta T_1 / \Delta T_2)} \quad (7)$$

In the equation, ΔT_1 and ΔT_2 are the temperature differences between the streams of each end of the heat exchangers.

The heat duty and the stream temperatures are results of the simulations, while the overall heat transfer coefficient values are taken from the literature (Aromada, 2020; Aromada et al., 2021; Aromada et al., 2022). The overall heat transfer coefficient depends on the fluids involved and the heat exchanger type. The type of exchanger and the overall heat transfer coefficient for each heat exchanger can be found in

Table 5
Dimensional assumptions for the column total height.

Columns internals	Addition	Reference
Packing height section [m]	Maximum between 10 and 12	(van der Spek et al., 2019)
Space between sections [m]	2.5 for $D \leq 8$ 4 for $D > 8$	(van der Spek et al., 2019)
Height for mist collector + gas outlet section [m]	2.5	(Kvamsdal et al., 2010)
Height required for flue gas inlet and distributor (between the sump and the first packed section) [m]	2 + 0.5D	(Kvamsdal et al., 2010)
Sump	It is determined assuming a residence time of 6 minutes.	(Kvamsdal et al., 2010)

Table 6
Specifications for the water wash column.

Parameter	Value/specification	Comments/ reference(s)
Packing Diameter	Mellapak 250Y Same as the absorber	(Tobiesen et al., 2007) –
Packing height [m]	4	(Dinh, 2023)
Water liquid/gas ratio [kg /kg]	1.3	(Drewry and Rochelle, 2024)

Table 7
Dimension factors and assumptions for the heat exchangers.

Types of heat exchangers	References	Overall heat transfer coefficient kW/m ² K	References
Reboiler	Kettle type (Aromada et al., 2021)	1.20	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Amine cooler	Plate and frame (Aromada et al., 2022)	1.00	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Rich/Lean condensers	Plate and frame (Aromada et al., 2022)	1.00	(Aromada, 2020)
	Plate and frame (Aromada et al., 2022)	1.00	(Aromada, 2020)

Table 7.

Plate and frame heat exchangers are used in this study. Shell and tube heat exchangers are more commonly used in process industry since they are capable of handling a wider range of operating conditions, with greater resilience for pressure and temperature differences (Aromada, 2020). However, plate heat exchangers can achieve higher overall heat transfer coefficients, and they also offer a large surface area per unit of volume, resulting in a more compact heat exchanger (Aromada, 2020), which is important when space availability can be a limit factor.

Each simulation provides the duty and temperatures for the amine cooler and condenser while assuming the inlet temperature of the cooling water stream as 20 °C and the outlet temperature of 30 °C. For the reboiler, its duty and cold stream temperatures are determined through simulation data. The hot stream utilized is low-pressure steam at 160 °C.

As all the heat exchangers modeled have process constraints, a design margin of 10 % was incorporated for each required heat exchanger area (IEAGHG, 2017b).

3.1.3. Pumps and blower

CO₂SIM was employed to determine the power needed for the pumps and the blower, even though those are not shown in the model flow-sheet, Fig. 1. The calculations were based on the flow rates obtained from the simulations, while the cooling water flow rates were determined based on the utility duties. The list of the additional pumps included in the model is shown in Table 8.

The second specification for the pump sizing is the total head loss that the fluid must overcome. This value was determined by calculating the specific head loss of each equipment situated downstream of the pump. Since this work also considers the distance between the sources and the location of the CO₂ capture plant equipment, it was necessary to account for the head loss associated with the distance. The increase of the pressure for the liquid transported is also important to prevent flashing inside the pipes.

The values and assumptions for this calculation are shown in Table 9.

The pump sizing incorporated an oversizing factor, which correlates with the pump-specific control. Details regarding the control and the corresponding factor can also be found in Table 8. The flue gas blower was sized with the same methodology employed for the pump.

Table 8
List of additional pumps included on the model.

	Type	Capacity/control	factor	Reference
Rich Pump	Centrifugal	Under level control	1.2	(IEAGHG, 2017c)
Lean Pump	Centrifugal	Under level control	1.2	(IEAGHG, 2017c)
Stripper condenser pump	Centrifugal	Under flow control	1.1	(IEAGHG, 2017c)
Cooling water pump	Centrifugal	Under flow control	1.1	(IEAGHG, 2017c)
Water wash pump	Centrifugal	Under flow control	1.1	(IEAGHG, 2017c)
Makeup pump	Centrifugal	Under flow control	1.1	(IEAGHG, 2017c)
Flue gas blower	Centrifugal	Under flow control	1.1	(IEAGHG, 2017c)

Table 9
Head loss taken into account for each equipment for the pump sizing.

Equipment	Head loss associated	References
Absorber	1.15 bar (packing related + DCC and blower) +0,1 bar/ meter of the total height	(Çengel and Cimbala, 2006)
Heat exchanger	0.5 bar	(Laval and Corporate, 2024)
Stripper	0.1 bar / meter of total height	(Çengel and Cimbala, 2006)
Flue gas pipeline	0.1 bar/ 100 m	(Turton; and Whiting, 2018)
Solvent pipeline	0.1 bar/ 100 m	(Turton; and Whiting, 2018)

3.1.4. Tanks

The solvent and water storage tanks were sized following the recommendations given by Towler and Sinnott (2020). The size of both tanks was determined based on the total solvent and water inventory needed for all equipment, including the columns, heat exchangers, and piping. Stainless steel was chosen as the material for both tanks to prevent corrosion and reduce solvent degradation (Hjelmaas et al., 2017). Additionally, for the solvent storage tanks themselves, it is advised to utilize nitrogen blankets to prevent degradation (Dow Chemical Company, 2022).

3.1.5. Spare equipment

To ensure uninterrupted operation and minimize downtime in the event of equipment failure, a usual strategic procedure is to include spare equipment as part of the operational framework (van der Spek et al., 2019). In this work, a spare was included for each pump, and for the heat exchanger and columns no spare parts were included.

3.2. Cost estimation

As highlighted by van der Spek et al. (2019) and Aromada et al. (2021), cost engineering and economics are essential in the evaluation of carbon capture technologies. These factors determine the feasibility and influence the decision-making process regarding technology choice and implementation.

Previous studies highlight significant disparities in capital cost estimates for CCS processes (Roussanaly et al., 2021a; van der Spek et al., 2019; Ali et al., 2019; Aromada et al., 2021; Rubin et al., 2013; Roussanaly et al., 2021b), with deviations up to 60 % observed even for identical installations (van der Spek et al., 2019). These discrepancies primarily arise from design and sizing errors in CCS equipment, such as the omission of some equipment or neglecting operating and safety margins (van der Spek et al., 2019). As the sizing and costing of individual equipment are fundamental to bottom-up capital cost estimates,

inaccuracies in bare equipment costs propagate to final CAPEX estimates.

Rubin et al. (2013) proposed a framework for estimating and reporting CCS capital and operating costs, emphasizing transparency in methodology and assumptions. It outlines the essential cost elements for CCS estimates and details financial analysis and cost metrics, particularly focusing on CCS projects from power plants (Ali et al., 2019). Transparent cost estimation methodologies are crucial for ensuring informed interpretation of costing studies.

The preliminary cost estimation methodology for the present work includes capital cost estimation and operating cost estimation. Further elaboration on these components is provided in the following subsections.

3.2.1. General assumptions

In the current study, the initial assumption proposed is that refinery production remains constant throughout the assessment period. Consequently, the processed crude oil and its derived products remain unchanged, ensuring consistency in the quantity of CO₂ within the flue gas streams.

The flue gas streams analyzed were considered pre-treated, with the pre-treatment units not included in the cost estimation analysis. Further, the cost analysis encompasses the CO₂ capture plant and the piping connecting the sources while excluding expenses related to CO₂ compression, transportation, sequestration, and monitoring.

The utilized factors and equations gave the cost in the 2001 US Gulf Coast basis (Turton and Whiting, 2018). Thus, correlation (Eq. (8)) was used to accommodate the time effect influence on the Purchased Equipment Cost ($C_{base\ year}$), as guided by the Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index (CEPCI).

$$C_{2023} = C_{2001} \frac{CEPCI_{2023}}{CEPCI_{2001}} \quad (8)$$

Additionally, the construction costs for an independent utilities plant catering to the required steam and power have been factored into the study.

3.2.2. Cost estimation methodology

The cost estimation was conducted following the methodology outlined by Turton and Whiting (2018), which, according to NETL (2021), would be considered the third level of a capital cost methodology, the Total Plant Cost, TPC, level. The main basis of the methodology is the cost of the major process equipment, taking into account the direct and indirect costs required for their construction and/or installation, and includes labour and processes contingencies (NETL 2021).

Initially, the bare module cost (C_{BM}) for the main equipment was calculated, which represents the sum of direct and indirect costs associated with each equipment. The C_{BM} proposed by Turton and Whiting (2018) is calculated using Eq. (9) and takes into account the direct and indirect costs of each equipment. Where C_p^0 is the purchased cost for base conditions: equipment made with the most common material, carbon steel (CS), and operating at ambient pressures; B_1 and B_2 are parameters specified for each equipment, F_p is the parameter that incorporates different operating pressure and F_M is a parameter to incorporate the different types of construction material. In this work, all equipment costs were calculated using stainless steel, SS, as the material of construction.

$$C_{BM} = C_p^0 [B_1 + B_2 F_p F_M] \quad (9)$$

To calculate the purchased cost for base conditions (C_p^0), Eq. (10) is used. K_1 , K_2 and K_3 are parameters characteristic for each unit and W is the capacity/size parameter specific to each equipment.

$$\log_{10}(C_p^0) = K_1 + K_2 \log_{10}(W) + K_3 [\log_{10}(W)]^2 \quad (10)$$

If the W value from the simulation exceeded the upper limit

applicable for the method, a power-law correlation, Eq. (11), was employed to adjust the cost in accordance with the unit capacity, as recommended by Turton and Whiting (2018).

$$\frac{C_a}{C_b} = \left(\frac{W_a}{W_b} \right)^n \quad (11)$$

where C_i is the purchased cost for base i , n is the cost exponent and the subscripts a and b refer to the equipment required attribute and the base attribute, respectively.

As the original method does not include the cost of the column's internals (Park and Øi, 2017; van der Spek et al., 2019), the procedure was supplemented with information gathered from the open literature to incorporate these elements into the cost estimations. To maintain the consistency of the method and its foundation, as previously mentioned, correlations were employed to adjust the effect of time (Eq. (8)) and location factors (Ferrari, 2019) to these elements.

Additional expenses related to contingencies (C_{cont}) and other charges (C_{fee}) are factored in to estimate the total (Banco Central do Brasil 2024) equipment costs (C_{TM}) (Turton and Whiting, 2018), as shown in Eq. (12).

$$C_{TM} = C_{BM} + C_{cont} + C_{fee} \quad (12)$$

As the total equipment costs refer to the cost of making small to moderate expansions or alterations in an existing plant, it is important to include the costs attributed to additional work, such as site development and auxiliary buildings, related to the installation of a completely new facility (Turton and Whiting, 2018). The grassroot cost (C_{GR}) (Turton and Whiting, 2018), the cost that refers to a completely new facility, is shown in Eq. (13).

$$C_{GR} = C_{TM} + 0.5 \sum_{i=1}^n C_{BM} \quad (13)$$

To determine the annualized installed cost (or annualized CAPEX), the initial step involves calculating the annualized factor using Eq. (14) (Ali et al., 2019), which relies on the interest rate p and the project life n of the plant. Eq. (14) is designed for a 1-year construction period and a 20-year operational lifespan. The annualized installed cost (in euros per year) is then computed by dividing the installed cost by the annualized factor, as described in Eq. (15).

$$\text{Annualized factor} = \sum_{n=1}^{20} \left[\frac{1}{(1+p)^n} \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Annualized CAPEX} = \frac{\text{Total Equipment Cost}}{\text{Annualized factor}} \quad (15)$$

The economic assumptions utilized to estimate the capital cost are outlined in Table 10.

Following the estimation of equipment costs, the process of determining the total manufacturing cost (COM) can start. Similar to equipment costs, manufacturing costs can be categorized. The categories are

Table 10
Assumptions for capital cost.

Parameter	Value	Reference
CAPEX	Total Equipment Cost	(Turton; and Whiting, 2018)
Cost year	802.6 (2023)	(Pinto et al., 2024)
Currency	US\$	(Turton; and Whiting, 2018)
Currency conversion rate [US\$ to €]	0.9219	(Banco Central do Brasil 2024)
Plant location	Netherlands	(Ali et al., 2019)
Project life	20 years	
Discount rate	8%	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Annual maintenance	3% CAPEX	(Aromada et al., 2021)

direct, fixed, and general expenses (Turton and Whiting, 2018). The manufacturing cost can be calculated as shown in Eq. (16).

$$COM = 0.181FCI + 2.73C_{OL} + 1.23(C_{UT} + C_{WT} + C_{RM}) \quad (16)$$

where, FCI is fixed capital investment, C_{OL} is the labor costs, C_{UT} the costs of utilities, C_{WT} is the waste treatment cost and C_{RM} is the cost related to raw materials (Turton and Whiting, 2018). The fixed operating cost will include the labour and maintenance expenses, while the variable operating cost will include the cost of electricity, steam, cooling water, and the solvent. The assumptions utilized to estimate the operating cost are outlined in Table 11.

3.2.3. Fluid transportation cost

Due to limited space availability near emission sources, existing industrial facilities often face challenges accommodating new facilities, such as CO₂ capture units. Consequently, one common approach to address this issue involves placing the new unit at a greater distance from the emission source (Roussanaly et al., 2021a; van der Spek et al., 2019) or placing the absorption section of an amine-based capture process near the CO₂ emission point while conveying the CO₂ absorbed in the rich solvent to a separate location for regeneration (Roussanaly et al., 2021a). By relocating the CO₂ capture unit to a more spacious area, industries can overcome spatial constraints while still implementing emission reduction technologies. Nevertheless, these approaches include transporting the CO₂ absorbed in the rich solvent for longer distances or the transportation of the flue gas over extended distances, which entails the use of large-diameter and costly stainless-steel ducting, and may entail modifications to the existing industrial infrastructure (Roussanaly et al., 2021a).

It is necessary to include the costs associated with the pipelines for flue gas and solvent transport. For the cost of the flue gas transportation, a simple correlation was developed using the data provided by Roussanaly et al. (2021a). This correlation relates the direct cost of pipeline installation to the volumetric flow rate of the flue gas and the distance between the source and the absorber section from 100 to 1000 m. For transporting the solvent over longer distances, a correlation was used that relates the cost per length to the material selected and the required nominal diameter of the pipeline (DACE, 2024). The solvent pipeline system requires two pipelines: one to pump the lean solvent from the stripper back to the absorbers and one to pump the rich solvent to the stripper. Since MEA is corrosive, the pipes used must be of stainless steel to prevent excessive corrosion and pitting. Hjelmaas et al. (2017) conducted tests using different corrosion coupons in a CO₂ capture plant at the CO₂ Technology Centre Mongstad, and proposed 304L and 316L stainless steel as good candidates.

In general, transporting the liquid solvent instead of flue gas is cheaper when it comes to pressurization costs and operating costs compared to transportation of flue gas requiring gas compressors. More details about the costs associated with fluid transportation are given in Section S3 of the supplementary information.

4. Results

For all sets, in each case, a series of simulations by varying the L/G

Table 11
Assumptions for operating cost.

Parameter	Unit	Value	Reference
Operating hours/year	hours/year	8000	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Electricity	€/kWh	0.104	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Steam	€/kWh	0.043	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Cooling water	€/m ³	0.030	(Aromada et al., 2021)
MEA	€/m ³	2017	(Aromada et al., 2021)
Operator	€/year	80,414	(Aromada et al., 2021)

*The values have been escalated to January 2023.

ratio was conducted. The objective was to calculate the reboiler duty required to achieve a 95 % capture rate, aiming to identify the optimal operating conditions from an energy perspective. For scenarios involving multiple absorbers and a combined-stripper, the total CO₂ capture rate for the plant, based on the combined CO₂ flow rate from all sources, was set at 95 %, rather than imposing a 95 % capture rate on each absorber. This approach was chosen to provide greater flexibility and broaden the range of potential outcomes.

Once the optimized operating conditions were found, the sizing and cost estimation were carried out. The simulation results and the techno-economic assessment will first be presented as individual cases. Subsequently, this section will focus on the potential combinations of cases from the three sets and discuss the options for managing the four different CO₂ sources.

The optimized operating conditions for Set I and Set III cases are presented in Table 12, which also contains the CO₂ content (wet basis) and the absorber geometry for each case. As discussed earlier, the optimal operating conditions, Table 12, determined in Set I, were used as the basis for Set II. It should be noted that in Set III, the volumetric flow rate of some combined flue gas streams has exceeded the values recommended by Duss and Menon (Duss and Menon, 2010), as previously discussed in Section 3.1.1. For these cases, the flue gas is split into two streams of equal volumetric flow rate, with two absorbers operating in parallel to treat the gas. The asterisk (*) in Table 12 indicates these cases.

Set II cases, with multiple absorbers, are presented Table 13. Different procedures were tested to find the optimal operating conditions when applying the multi-absorber/combined-stripper approach for two different sources. The main difference between the procedures lies in how the total amount of solvent, and the solvent split fraction were defined in the base case for each study. Also, a sensitivity analysis of the solvent split fraction was performed. In this sensitivity analysis, the search for the optimal conditions is carried out for each split fraction. More detailed information can be found in Section S5 from supplementary file. In this table, the row identified by ‘‘Approach’’ shows which method provided the best simulation results: LG_opt, greater α , smaller α or the mathematical model.

When comparing the results from Set I for individual sources (Table 12) with the results obtained on the combined sources from Set II (Table 13), it is notable that at the optimal point, the values from Set II achieved different loadings, and, generally, smaller L/G ratios for each absorber.

Further details about the simulations, such as the temperature and the loading profiles, can be found in sections S4, S6, and S7 in the supplementary file. Throughout all simulations, the absorber temperature and loading profile were monitored to prevent operating issues, like when the driven force gradient becomes so small, leading to an increase in energy consumption, operating costs, and operational instability.

Figs. 4–6 illustrate the results of the techno-economic assessment for each case: the total equipment cost, the total cost per ton of CO₂ captured, and the variable operating cost per ton of CO₂ captured, respectively. The values can be found in Section S9 in the supplementary information. Each set is identified by a shaded background colour: yellow for Set I, blue for Set II and pink for Set III.

Fig. 4 details the capital cost of the main equipment. The percentage ratio between the individual cost of these components and the total cost is shown in Table 14. The most expensive components are the absorber column, the stripper column, and the rich/lean heat exchanger. The high cost of the columns is attributed to the price of the packing material used, which can vary depending on the choice of packing type. A sensitivity analysis will be conducted later in this study to account for this variability.

The capital cost of Set I can be found in the yellow-shaded area in Fig. 4. In Set I, a CO₂ capture plant was evaluated for each source. As expected, Source A exhibited the highest cost due to its lower CO₂ partial pressure and greater flue gas flow rate, leading to larger equipment and

Table 12
Process simulation results for each case from Set I and Set III.

	Set I				Set III				ABD*	ACD*	BCD	ABCD*			
	A	B	C	D	AB*	AC*	AD	BC					BD	CD	ABC*
% CO ₂ (wet basis)	4	8.5	11	20	5.08	4.95	5.17	9.33	10.8	14.0	5.71	5.92	5.91	10.86	6.43
Packing height [m]	23	17	16	16	19	19	19	17	17	17	19	19	19	17	19
Absorber Diameter [m]	15.5	8.7	6.1	4.3	12.5	12	16	11	10	7.5	13	13	12.1	11	13.5
α_{lean} [mol CO ₂ / mol amine]	0.178	0.168	0.178	0.179	0.175	0.171	0.164	0.161	0.177	0.177	0.173	0.165	0.172	0.163	0.179
α_{rich} [mol CO ₂ / mol amine]	0.487	0.493	0.491	0.488	0.485	0.486	0.485	0.495	0.496	0.495	0.489	0.492	0.490	0.495	0.491
Rich Solvent Temperature [°C]	41.9	42.7	44.2	50.7	42.0	42.0	41.9	42.5	43.8	45.8	42.1	42.0	42.1	43.5	42.2
L/G [kg / kg]	0.93	1.81	2.41	4.23	1.17	1.13	1.12	1.90	2.36	3.00	1.29	1.29	1.32	2.26	1.47
Reboiler Temperature [°C]	120.9	121.1	120.9	120.8	120.9	121.0	121.2	121.2	120.9	120.9	121.0	121.1	120.9	121.2	120.8
SRD [GJ / ton _{CO₂}]	3.56	3.52	3.54	3.61	3.57	3.55	3.49	3.47	3.53	3.57	3.55	3.54	3.54	3.53	3.54
Temperature on the top of the absorber [°C]	49.1	52.6	53.1	53.3	50.19	50.09	50.49	53.15	53.02	53.65	50.8	51.1	50.9	53.7	51.2
Temperature on the top of the stripper [°C]	105.4	105.4	105.4	105.6	105.49	105.49	105.35	105.18	105.32	105.43	105.4	105.5	105.7	105.4	105.3
Steam [MW]	87.98	57.50	37.31	34.79	145.69	124.40	118.98	93.27	91.94	72.12	182.30	178.57	157.9	128.97	216.06

* The flue gas was split into two equal parts, resulting in two absorption sections in parallel.

a higher packing height in the absorber.

The blue-shaded area in Fig. 4 shows the capital cost of the main equipment of Set II. This graph only considers the equipment related to the CO₂ capture plant. The cost associated with solvent transportation, including the necessary equipment and electricity, will be presented and discussed later. As expected, this setup results in higher costs associated with the absorber column since multiple columns are required. Due to the increased volume of gas needing treatment, a larger quantity of solvent is necessary. This leads to larger and more numerous heat exchangers and utilities, although only a single stripper column is utilized for regeneration.

The pink shaded area in Fig. 4 shows the results for Set III. Similarly to Set II, this graph only considers the equipment related to the CO₂ capture plant. The cost associated with the flue gas transportation, including the necessary equipment and electricity, will be presented and discussed later. In Set III, it is evident that the cost associated with the absorber column and the lean/rich heat exchanger have also increased significantly compared to Set I. In this particular set, the increased amounts of gas and liquid have demanded larger equipment and a greater number of heat exchangers and utilities, while it was feasible to use a combined stripper column. The final dimensions and number of equipment aligned with the limits suggested by Duss and Menon (2010) and van der Spek et al. (2019).

When comparing the flue gas mixing approach to the multiple absorber combined stripper approach, for example, case AB with case A_B, the absorber cost is higher for the multiple absorber approach (A_B), which is expected since this approach involves more columns, resulting in approximately a 25 % cost increase. For the stripper cost, the difference between these approaches is less than 2 %. This is expected since the stripper dimensions are designed based on the total volumetric flue gas rate to be treated. The lean-rich heat exchanger shows a cost difference between the two approaches, ranging from 14 % to 25 %.

Fig. 5 displays the total cost per ton of CO₂ captured, divided into CAPEX, fixed OPEX and variable OPEX. It is evident that the cost associated with the OPEX encompasses a significant portion of the total cost. This is a consequence of amine-based CO₂ capture being an energy-intensive process due to the energy required for amine regeneration.

Fig. 5 shows the total plant cost per ton of CO₂. For Set I it varies from 115 to 136 €/ton_{CO₂captured}, for Set II it ranges from 92 to 111 €/ton_{CO₂captured}, and for Set III it varies from 100 to 134 €/ton_{CO₂captured} for 95 % captured rate. As shown in Fig. 5, the total cost per ton of CO₂ for Set II is less expensive compared to Set I and Set III. This is because capturing CO₂ from multiple sources with a single plant results in a greater overall capture CO₂ amount. Additionally, having only a central regeneration site reduces the capital cost of equipment. This has reduced the total amount of solvent required to achieve the desired capture, consequently reducing the total amount of heat required per ton of CO₂.

Fig. 6 presents the variable operating cost per ton of CO₂ captured, including electricity, steam, cooling water and solvent expenses. As expected, steam consumption incurs the highest expenses. In this work, as also in Ali et al. (2019), the steam costs are considered to be purchased from an external supplier. However, an industrial cluster, such as a refinery, can produce its own steam and use it in the CO₂ capture plant, potentially reducing the operating cost. Consequently, a sensitivity analysis of the price of steam has been carried out. As previously explained, the case studies in Set II required less solvent when compared to Set I cases, resulting in a lower heat demand for its regeneration. This led to a reduced heat requirement and a decrease in the steam consumption per ton of CO₂, as illustrated in Fig. 6.

4.1. Combinations of sets I, II, and III that provide 95 % capture from stacks A, B, C and D

This subsection presents the possible combined configurations for

Table 13
Process simulation results for each case from Set II.

Approach	A_B Greater α	A_C LG_opt	A_D LG_opt	B_C Smaller α	B_D Smaller α	C_D Smaller α	A_B_C LG_opt	A_B_D LG_opt	A_C_D LG_opt	B_C_D LG_opt	A_B_C_D LG_opt
α_{lean} [mol CO ₂ /mol amine]	0.174	0.169	0.179	0.175	0.174	0.173	0.175	0.176	0.181	0.181	0.175
$\alpha_{rich, 1}$ [mol CO ₂ /mol amine]	0.488	0.488	0.476	0.494	0.484	0.496	0.481	0.481	0.484	0.494	0.481
$\alpha_{rich, 2}$ [mol CO ₂ /mol amine]	0.491	0.492	0.501	0.488	0.498	0.476	0.498	0.498	0.493	0.482	0.498
$\alpha_{rich, 3}$ [mol CO ₂ /mol amine]	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.493	0.491	0.493	0.482	0.493
$\alpha_{rich, 42}$ [mol CO ₂ /mol amine]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.491
(L/G) ₁ [kg/kg]	0.92	0.90	1.00	1.86	1.96	2.34	0.96	0.96	0.96	1.90	0.96
(L/G) ₂ [kg/kg]	1.89	2.37	3.86	2.46	3.96	4.43	1.81	1.81	2.40	2.52	1.81
(L/G) ₃ [kg/kg]	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.40	4.20	4.22	4.41	2.52
(L/G) ₄ [kg/kg]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.20
SRD [GJ /ton _{CO₂}]	3.54	3.53	3.64	3.55	3.58	3.59	3.57	3.56	3.58	3.58	3.56
CO ₂ recovery 1(%)	95	95	97	94	97	94	97	97	96	94	97
CO ₂ recovery 2(%)	95	95	89	96	92	96	92	92	93	96	92
CO ₂ recovery 3(%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	95	95	94	96	95
CO ₂ recovery 4(%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	95
Total CO ₂ recovery	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95	95
Top Fraction 01 (β_1)	0.60	0.70	0.75	0.60	0.65	0.50	0.50	0.51	0.56	0.44	0.41
Top Fraction 02 (β_2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.6	0.6	0.52	0.52	0.44
Top Fraction 03 (β_3)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.51

Fig. 4. Total Equipment Cost for Set I (yellow shaded area), Set II (blue shaded area) and Set III (pink shaded area). The multiple-absorber, combined-stripper approach is tagged using the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B); cases with mixing of different flue gas streams, the letters of the sources are listed without spaces between them (e.g., AB) with one absorber and one stripper; * means that two absorbers parallel are used due to high flue gas amount treated.

treating the four sources of CO₂ emission, using the previous results obtained for Set I, II, and III. The costs of these configurations are illustrated from the least to most expensive in Figs. 7-9.

Fig. 7 illustrates the equipment installation cost for various scenarios where all four stacks (A, B, C, and D) are being treated. The results indicate that different configurations generally result in lower equipment installation costs compared to the case with the multiple-absorber/combined-stripper approach for all four stacks (A_B_C_D). When comparing this with the scenario where each source has an individual plant, A + B + C + D, the total cost for the absorbers are the same. However, the stripper cost is lower in A_B_C_D configuration since it utilizes only one stripper column, which has a smaller volume compared to the combined volume of the four individual stripper columns from A + B + C + D. On the other hand, the area required for the lean-rich heat exchanger is larger in A_B_C_D than the one required for four individuals

plants. This is because A_B_C_D must handle a greater volume of rich amine solvent at once. Consequently, the increased lean-rich heat exchanger cost outweighs the savings from the stripper cost, leading to a higher installation cost in the end.

The changes in the stripper and lean-rich heat exchanger costs are also detected in the flue gas mix case ABCD*, which ranks as the second most expensive. In the ABCD scenario, the two absorbers are less expensive than the four absorbers in the A_B_C_D case, justifying a lower total cost. The ABCD* configuration is approximately €14 million cheaper than A_B_C_D. However, it is important to note that the flue gas transportation costs are not included in this analysis.

In the combined configurations shown in Fig. 7, the total cost of the absorbers ranges from €65 million to €81 million, with CD + A_B configuration being the least expensive and A_D + B_C being the most expensive. The stripper cost varies from €20 million to €42 million, with

Fig. 5. Total Cost per ton of captured CO₂ for Set I (yellow shaded area), Set II (blue shaded area) and Set III (pink shaded area). The multiple-absorber, combined-stripper approach is tagged using the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B); cases with mixing of different flue gas streams, the letters of the sources are listed without spaces between them (e.g., AB) with one absorber and one stripper; * means that two absorbers parallel are used due to high flue gas amount treated.

Fig. 6. Variable operating cost per ton of captured CO₂ for Set I (yellow shaded area), Set II (blue shaded area), and Set III (pink shaded area). The multiple-absorber, combined-stripper approach is tagged using the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B); cases with mixing of different flue gas streams, the letters of the sources are listed without spaces between them (e.g., AB) with one absorber and one stripper; * means that two absorbers parallel are used due to high flue gas amount treated.

BD + A_C being the least expensive and A+B+C+D being the most expensive. The cost of the lean-rich exchanger ranges from €24 million to €73 million, with A+B+C+D being the cheaper and A_B_C_D the most expensive.

Fig. 7 indicates that combining flue gases or combining absorbers leads into lower equipment costs. However, it should be noted that the

costs in the figure do not include any solvent or flue gas transport costs or spatial constraints at the industrial site. These factors could make these alternatives more expensive in different ways. Thus the distance between sources and spatial constraints would change the ranking in Fig. 7.

The total costs, including OPEX and the annualized CAPEX, are

Table 14
Share of the main CO₂ capture plant equipment on the total equipment cost.

Simulation	Absorber	Stripper	Lean/rich heat Exchanger
A	41 %	16 %	11 %
B	30 %	18 %	15 %
C	30 %	21 %	7 %
D	26 %	20 %	7 %
A_B	39 %	12 %	17 %
A_C	39 %	13 %	16 %
A_D	40 %	8 %	18 %
B_C	32 %	13 %	14 %
B_D	30 %	14 %	14 %
C_D	29 %	18 %	13 %
A_B_C	35 %	8 %	24 %
A_B_D	33 %	11 %	22 %
A_C_D	39 %	10 %	18 %
B_C_D	29 %	12 %	20 %
A_B_C_D	31 %	10 %	29 %
AB *	38 %	9 %	19 %
AC *	38 %	10 %	17 %
AD	34 %	15 %	19 %
BC	30 %	16 %	15 %
BD	28 %	16 %	17 %
CD	26 %	17 %	18 %
ABC*	33 %	8 %	26 %
ABD *	33 %	8 %	25 %
ACD	24 %	12 %	34 %
BCD	24 %	13 %	26 %
ABCD *	29 %	7 %	33 %

* Two absorbers in parallel.

described in Fig. 8. As this analysis takes into account the amount of CO₂ captured per retrofitted plant, A_B_C_D and ABCD presented the lowest cost per ton of CO₂, while the case with all individual plants illustrated the highest cost per ton of CO₂. It was expected that combinations between plants that capture more than one source of CO₂ simultaneously would present lower values, as they capture more with lower operating costs. Fig. 9 illustrates the variable cost per ton of CO₂ for different configurations. Since the steam share constitutes the majority of the variable cost, the trend in the variable cost per ton of CO₂ mirrors the trend in the total cost per ton of CO₂, Fig. 8.

4.2. Fluid transportation costs

The flue gas transportation cost is a function of the flue gas volumetric flow rate, leading to significant cost differences between the different investigated sources. The installation of flue gas pipelines, in addition to the compression system, can reach around 10⁷ € for longer distances as seen in Fig. S4 in supplementary material, potentially increasing the total equipment cost by at least 10 %.

For the solvent transportation, the installation costs were calculated using two different materials: stainless steel 316L and stainless steel 304L (Fig. S3 from the Supplementary file). The solvent transportation cost is a function of the pipeline nominal diameter, which was determined based on the lean amine and the rich amine flow rate for each case. As expected and seen in Fig. S5 in the supplementary information, the costs with 316L are typically 25 % higher compared to 304L. Thus, using 304L when possible is recommended. The installation cost of the solvent pipeline network varies from 10⁵ to 10⁶ €, while the total equipment installation cost of a CO₂ capture plant is approximately 10⁸ € (See Fig. 7), indicating that solvent transportation has a minimal impact on the total cost.

Depending on the distance of the sources and the absorption plant location, incorporating the cost of the flue gas transportation into the total cost detailed in the previous section could potentially change the economics of the different scenarios.

4.3. Sensitivity analysis

According to Table 14 and Fig. 7, the absorber and stripper columns account for over 45 % of the total equipment cost in a CO₂ capture plant. A significant portion of this high cost is attributed to the price of the packing material used in these columns. As shown in Table 15, the cost of the packing material alone constitutes about 10 to 30 % of the total equipment cost. A simple study was conducted to examine the impact of a 50 % reduction in the price of the packing material. The results indicate that this price reduction could lead to a 10 to 30 % decrease in the total equipment cost, as shown in Table 15.

As it can be seen in Table 15, the steam cost represents between 50 and 74 % of the total operating expenses. These costs can vary significantly depending on the location and the availability of steam within the industrial complex. To better understand this influence, the OPEX was calculated, with steam costs being 50 % cheaper and 50 % more

Fig. 7. Total Equipment Cost for the possible configuration for the four CO₂ sources. The multiple-absorber, combined-stripper approach is tagged using the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B); cases with mixing of different flue gas streams, the letters of the sources are listed without spaces between them (e.g., AB) with one absorber and one stripper; * means that two absorbers parallel are used due to high flue gas amount treated.

Fig. 8. Total cost per ton of captured CO₂ for the possible configuration for the four CO₂ sources. The multiple-absorber, combined-stripper approach is tagged using the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B); cases with mixing of different flue gas streams, the letters of the sources are listed without spaces between them (e.g., AB) with one absorber and one stripper; * means that two absorbers parallel are used due to high flue gas amount treated.

Fig. 9. Variable operating cost per ton of captured CO₂ for the possible configuration between the four CO₂ sources. The multiple-absorber, combined-stripper approach is tagged using the letters representing the sources with an underscore symbol between them (e.g., A_B); cases with mixing of different flue gas streams, the letters of the sources are listed without spaces between them (e.g., AB) with one absorber and one stripper; * means that two absorbers parallel are used due to high flue gas amount treated.

expensive. A 50 % change in the steam costs leads to a decrease or an increase of up to 33 %.

5. Conclusions

This paper investigated the feasibility of CO₂ capture at a multiple-source industrial site, evaluating various configurations to treat all of them, with a particular focus on the multi-absorber/combined-stripper approach. It also considers the option of individual CO₂ capture plants for each source as well as the possibility of a unique CO₂ capture plant treating multiple sources.

The multi-absorber/combined-stripper and the flue gas mixing

approaches can be attractive for industrial sites with limited space around CO₂ sources. However, these approaches require an additional infrastructure for fluid transportation: for the solvent between absorption and regeneration sites and for the flue gas from the source to the absorption site, respectively, which has been considered in the present work.

All the simulations were performed on an in-house software, CO₂SIM, and optimized using an in-house Matlab routine. Once the optimal operating conditions were identified, a preliminary sizing and cost assessment were conducted. Finally, the results were compared and discussed.

Simulations' results indicated that the multiple absorber one stripper

Table 15
Packing material and Steam cost sensitivity analysis.

Case	Packing Material			Steam					
	% on the total equipment cost		% reduction of total equipment cost	Current steam cost	50 % cheaper		50 % more expensive		
	Current packing cost	50 % cheaper		% on the total OPEX	% on the total OPEX	Reduction on OPEX	% on the total OPEX	Increase on OPEX	
A	34 %	21 %	27 %	48 %	30 %	21 %	59 %	21	
B	17 %	9 %	23 %	66 %	47 %	29 %	77 %	29 %	
C	12 %	6 %	24 %	64 %	45 %	28 %	75 %	28 %	
D	7 %	4 %	22 %	66 %	47 %	29 %	77 %	29 %	
A_B	29 %	17 %	14 %	45	29 %	22 %	55 %	22 %	
A_C	29 %	17 %	14 %	43 %	28 %	22 %	53 %	22 %	
A_D	27 %	16 %	14 %	44 %	28 %	223 %	54 %	22 %	
B_C	16 %	8 %	8 %	48 %	31 %	24 %	58 %	24 %	
B_D	15 %	8 %	7 %	49	32 %	24 %	59 %	24 %	
C_D	12 %	7 %	6 %	499 %	32 %	24 %	59 %	24 %	
A_B_C	22 %	12 %	11 %	46 %	30 %	23 %	57 %	23 %	
A_B_D	23 %	13 %	12 %	46 %	30 %	23 %	56 %	23 %	
A_C_D	25 %	14 %	12 %	47,	31 %	24 %	58 %	24 %	
B_C_D	12 %	7 %	6 %	51 %	34 %	25 %	61 %	25 %	
A_B_C_D	20 %	11 %	10 %	46 %	309 %	23 %	56 %	23 %	
AB *	25 %	9 %	32 %	65 %	45 %	29 %	75 %	29 %	
AC *	25 %	9 %	33 %	63 %	43 %	28 %	74 %	28 %	
AD	28 %	16 %	23 %	65 %	45 %	29 %	76 %	29 %	
BC	20 %	10 %	22 %	71 %	51 %	31 %	81 %	31 %	
BD	17 %	9 %	21 %	71 %	52 %	32 %	81 %	32 %	
CD	13 %	7 %	21 %	72 %	53 %	32 %	82 %	32 %	
ABC*	22 %	7 %	28 %	66 %	47 %	29 %	77 %	29 %	
ABD *	22 %	7 %	28 %	66 %	47 %	29 %	77 %	29 %	
ACD*	19 %	9 %	17 %	54 %	38 %	29 %	63 %	29 %	
BCD	16 %	8 %	18 %	74 %	54 %	32 %	83 %	32 %	
ABCD *	20 %	6 %	25 %	66 %	47 %	29 %	77 %	29 %	

* Two absorbers in parallel.

cases required slightly less solvent to achieve the desired capture rate compared to individual absorber setup, which also led to a lower reboiler duty on the regeneration of the total solvent amount. However, during the sizing and cost assessment, configurations handling more than one source simultaneously showed a greater initial investment cost once these cases had to treat greater volumes of gas and manage larger solvent amounts, leading to larger equipment. When comparing the multiple absorber one stripper and the flue gas mixing approach, in terms of equipment cost investment, including only the CO₂ capture plant retrofitting, the multiple absorber one stripper was more expensive. Nonetheless, it demonstrated lower operating expenses. When evaluating all possible configurations to treat all four sources simultaneously, combinations with more individual CO₂ capture plants showed higher operating expenses per ton of CO₂ captured. Excluding the cost associated with the fluid transport from the sizing and cost assessment, the flue gas mixing approach was less costly than the multi-absorber/combined-stripper approach. However, the fluid transportation costs assessment revealed that flue gas transportation could increase the total cost by at least 10 %, depending on the distance between the sources and the absorption site. In contrast, solvent transportation costs did not significantly impact the cost regardless of the distances involved. This finding could shift the cost comparison between these configurations.

Finally, the packing and the steam costs have a significant impact on the total costs. A 50 % reduction in packing costs could lower the capital expenditure by 10 to 30 %, while a reduction in the steam cost would result in at least 25 % decrease in the operating costs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andressa Nakao: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Diego Morlando:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Hanna K. Knuutila:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Simulation tool was used. We are not allowed to share the codes.

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